

Dietary Lipid, Palmitate, Alters Critical Metabolic Reprogramming Genes in Meningioma

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Abstract

The strong correlation between cancer and poor dietary habits such as high sugar and fat intake has been known for decades. However, only after the recent metabolomics revolution, we began to unravel how poor diet and metabolic reprogramming help cancer to adapt and thrive. Recently, aberrant fatty acid (FA) metabolism gained attention as a critical metabolic adaptation enabling cancer survival. Hence, FA targeting approaches emerged as therapeutic options for several cancers including breast cancer, prostate cancer and gliomas. In the present study, we investigated the effect of dietary lipid palmitate on metabolic reprogramming of meningiomas, the most common primary adult brain tumor. Similar to gliomas, meningiomas also show dysregulated FA metabolism which correlates with worse prognosis. Yet the underlying molecular pathways of this phenomena remains undiscovered to date. To tackle these pathways, we modeled meningioma pathology using well-established meningioma cell lines: IOMM-Lee, CH157-MN and AC599 each representing different molecular and histopathological characteristics of the disease. We exposed meningioma cell lines to varying doses of palmitate to determine their corresponding IC50 values. As a result of our dose response studies, we concluded extracellular palmitate exerts cytotoxic effect on all cell lines at high dose and long-term exposure. Effect of palmitate on cell viability is comparable within IOMM Lee, CH157-MN and AC599. Next, in order to delineate the effects of palmitate on gene expression we exposed cells to 200 uM palmitate for 24 hours and evaluated differential gene expression using QPCR assay. Among genes investigated, Aldehyde Oxidase1(AOX1) which encodes an adipogenic/xenobiotic enzyme showed a significant down regulation in malignant cell lines CH157-MN and IOMM- Lee, while it was slightly upregulated in benign cell line AC599. Our results align with the findings of others showing that AOX1 plays a role in a fatty acid metabolic reprogramming. Moreover, down regulation of AOX1 was positively correlated with tumor grade. This suggests that AOX1 downregulation can enable survival of meningiomas in challenging environments and foster tumorigenic behavior. Finally, our findings indicates that FA-AOX1 axis could be exploited for drug targeting studies for treatment of malignant meningiomas.

Keywords: Tumour microenvironment, Meningioma, Palmitate, Gene Expression, AOX1

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1. Introduction

Cancer is the plague of 21st century. Combat against cancer has been successful in certain cancer types, yet there is still an urgent need for effective prevention or

treatment for many other cancers. Over the decades, researchers identified variety of risk factors for the deadly disease. Among those the most prevalent one is poor dietary habits. In fact, research shows 5.2% of all cancers has been related to bad food choices and %40

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of cancers could be prevented by choosing a healthy life style such as adapting a diet rich in fibers, low in refined products and fat (1,2). Excessive fat and sugar content in modern western diets are thought to alter cellular metabolism fostering tumor initiation and progression (3).

Lipids, mostly obtained through ingested fat in our diet, are essential biomolecules for all cells in the body. They serve as energy source, signaling molecules in the cell and precursors for membranous organelles' production and maintenance. Numerous cancers show dysregulated or altered lipid metabolism facilitating biomass and energy production required for tumor growth (5,11). Recently, malignancies such as breast and prostate cancer have been shown to extensively depend on environmental lipids to sustain tumorigenesis. In such lipogenic cancers, membrane production, posttranslational modifications of oncogenic proteins as well as energy supply & storage have been shown to rely on dysregulated lipid metabolism and have been linked to disease onset, drug resistance and metastasis (3,10,29). Moreover, adipocytes, the fat cells in the tissue, have been discovered to potentiate tumor initiation via activating oncogenic precursors. In light of these findings, role of surrounding fat tissue in cancers has gained attention (5).

Brain is an extremely lipid rich organ with %60 fat ratio. Increased fatty acid content has been reported for human intracranial tumors for more than 50 years. Yet it was not until the last decade scientists started to unravel the impact of lipid metabolism for brain neoplasms. For Glioblastoma Multiform(GBM), the deadliest of all brain tumors, lipid metabolisms emerged as a facilitating hallmark and a promising therapeutic option: de novo fatty acid synthesis inhibitor fatostatin stands out as an attractive drug and is being investigated in clinical trials for glioma treatment along with several other cancers (23,24). Given patterns in the lipid metabolism is tied to chemoresistance and proliferation in brain tumors such as GBM, drugs targeting altered lipidomic/metabolic pathways hold promise as a mean to cure other brain tumors.

Like GBMs recent studies on meningioma patient samples also show that dysregulated fatty acid metabolism is related to poor prognosis (25). However, molecular mechanism of tumorigenic fatty acid metabolism remains elusive. In our study we ,therefore, wanted to evaluate the fatty acid metabolism in meningioma

which is the most common primary brain tumor seen in adults. Despite its frequency in the population, meningioma treatment is still limited to resection or radiation therapy with high risk of recurrence (26). Hence, there is an urgent need for effective meningioma treatments.

2. Experimental/Methodology/Design

2.1 Reagents

High glucose Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) and Trypsin EDTA Solution A were purchased from Sartorius (Göttingen, Germany). Palmitate were purchased from Adooq Biosciences (Irvine, United States). BSA was bought from AmericanBio, Inc (Canton, United States). Primers, as shown in the Supplementary Table 1, was designed using Primer 3 Plus software (<https://www.primer3plus.com/>) and ordered from Oligomer. (Ankara, Turkey)

Understanding the role of fatty acid metabolism in meningiomas could potentially help us to identify viable drug targets for the treatment of the disease. In this project, we aim to understand the effect of palmitate, a common extracellular dietary lipid, on meningioma pathogenesis and identify differentially regulated genes in response to environmental palmitate levels. Our findings and others suggest that meningioma cells of various grades and genetic backgrounds respond differently to changes in extracellular fatty acids levels (27). We sought to model this aspect of meningioma pathology using different cell lines from various backgrounds and each grade. We utilized well established meningioma cell lines each bare various characterized mutations. Those cell lines were IOMM Lee, CH157-MN to representing malignant tumors (Grade III, II respectively) and AC599(BenMen) representing grade I benign meningiomas (28). To determine the extracellular fatty acids levels to which all meningioma cell lines can be exposed to without severe cytotoxicity, we performed dose-response experiments hence calculated IC50 values of each cell line. Our analysis showed us the levels tolerated by each cell line is comparable. Consequently, to keep the extracellular level of palmitate as the only variable in our study we decided to treat all cell lines with constant 200 um palmitate then to evaluate changes in expression of possibly lipid regulated metabolic genes. Since our ultimate goal is to

undercover the genes that are responsive to microenvironmental palmitate, we decided on 24-hour palmitate treatment allowing cellular metabolism to adapt to lipid alternation in the media. Utilizing a knowledge-based approach, we determine a list of such genes relevant to meningiomas: For that, we processed RNAseq data from our library we have built for our cell lines using a powerful, curated data base tool: Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA). IPA identified AOX1, SLC9A3R1, FABP6, CACNA1, and LRP2 as genes of interest. Following 24-hour, 200 μ M palmitate treatment, we have checked the expression of candidate genes via QPCR. Analysis of QPCR results for differentially regulated genes showed us expression of AOX1 gene significantly changes as a response to increased lipid content in the cell media. Our data indicates that malignant meningioma cell lines, CH157-MN and IOMM Lee, might be utilizing down regulation of AOX1 as a mean to adapt to increasing palmitate levels. All together our work suggests that for meningioma pathology, AOX1 might be an important regulator of metabolic response orchestrating the adaptation to changes in microenvironmental fatty acid levels.

2.2 Cell Culture

IOMM Lee, Benmen 599 and CH157 cell lines were grown at T25 flasks and 20 cm culture dish in the incubator of 37 °C with 5% CO₂. Cells were cultured with high glucose DMEM supplemented with %10 FBS and %1 PenStrep. (Biological Industries, USA). Growth medium was changed once in every two days.

2.3 Preparation of Palmitate Treatment

Palmitate should be solubilized and conjugated to BSA to be used for treatment of cells. This was achieved by modifying a method described previously by Kim et al (7). Briefly, 500 mM palmitate was prepared in 1 mL of %100 ethanol at 70°C and %10 BSA, that does not include free fatty acids, was solubilized with DMEM at 37°C. The DMEM-BSA mixture was filtered with a Minisart syringe filter. To 1mL aliquot of DMEM- BSA mix, 10 μ L palmitate was added while the mixture was being vortexed. Palmitic acid- BSA mixture was incubated at 55°C for 15 minutes. The conjugation of palmitate and BSA was achieved by using water sonication for 15 minutes. After conjugation, the mixture was incubated at 55°C for 15 minutes. 10 μ L of %100 ethanol was used in 1 mL

DMEM-BSA solution as vehicle control. Both vehicle control and treatment were stored at -20°C and melted at 55 °C before the treatment process.

2.4 MTT Assay

Extracellular lipids' effects on various cancer types and genetic profiles are known to vary. As a result, we initially sought to determine how much extracellular lipids each cell line can withstand without experiencing significant cytotoxicity. For this, we calculated IC₅₀ values. Cells were treated with different concentrations of Palmitate from 100 to 700 μ M for 48 hours. After treatment, MTT assay was used to examine cell viability of three cell lines. (Serva,Germany)MTT was mixed with PBS to create 5 mg/ml concentration and 100 μ L was added to each well. After 4-hour incubation at 37°C, MTT crystals were solubilized with SDS-HCl mixture by adding 1 mL to each well followed overnight incubation. Cell viability was measured at 570 nm absorbance. Absorbance values were used to calculate viability. Graphs were drawn using GraphPad Prism 8.

2.5 Computational Analysis

To identify target genes, RNA-sequencing results of IOMM Lee, BenMen 599 and CH157-MN cell line was processed by Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA©Qiagen). After the analysis, prospective target genes and their interacting pathways were validated with the help of String (<https://string-db.org>).

2.6 qPCR

After 24-hour treatment, RNA was isolated with TRIzol-based protocol. In summary, 500 μ L TRIZOL was added to cells under the hood and mixed with pipetting. (QIAGEN, USA) The lysate was collected and incubated for 5 minutes at room temperature. 100 μ L of chloroform was added with 3 minutes incubation at room temperature. The mixture was centrifuged at 12,000 rcf for 15 minutes at 4°C. Aqueous phase was transferred into a new Eppendorf tube. Then, 250 μ L of isopropanol was added followed by 10 minutes incubation at room temperature. The mixture was centrifuged for 10 minutes and washed with 500 μ L %75 ethanol followed by centrifugation at 7500 rcf for 5 minutes at 4°C. After removing supernatant and drying RNA pellet, the pellet was solubilized with 25 μ L nuclease free water and quantified using BioDrop. Accordingly,, high-quality RNA was processed to cDNA with iScript cDNA synthesis kit. The qPCR reaction was done

by using corresponding template cDNA dilutions and primers for target genes (FABP6, AOX1, LPR2, CA-CNA1A, SLC9A3R1) for each control and treatment group in every cell line. Then, Syber Green Master Mix was added for amplification process. (Promega,USA) After the completing this step, the plate was sent to the machine.(BioRad ,USA)

2.7 Data Analysis

All the experiments were made in triplicate and repeated three times. Relative mRNA expression levels were determined according to 2- $\Delta\Delta CT$ method (Bio-Rad RT qPCR Data Analysis Template). Data that are under 0.05 as p-value was considered statistically significant.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Meningioma cells shows different responses to different concentrations of palmitate

Our hypothesis stems from the data that lipid metabolism is differentially regulated in relation to tumor grades in meningiomas. (25) We use different meningioma cell lines IOMM Lee, CH157 MN & AC599 corresponding to different genetic backgrounds and grades to model meningioma pathology in vitro. IOMM Lee is the representative for Grade III (anaplastic) meningiomas, CH 157 MN is the representative for Grade II (atypical), and AC599 is the representative for Grade I (benign) meningiomas (28). It is known that effect of extracellular lipids varies for different types cancers from different genetic makeup. Therefore, we wanted firstly explore amount of extracellular lipids each cell line can tolerate without serious cytotoxicity. To do so we determined IC50 values.

We exposed our cell lines to a variety of concentration of palmitate treatment from 100 μM to 700 μM to find toxic effect. The concentrations were chosen after many literatures search and calculated as seven serial dilutions; that are 100 μM , 138 μM , 191 μM , 265 μM , 366 μM , 506 μM and 700 μM , of BSA-conjugated palmitate mixture for 48 hours.

Our dose response analyses led us to the conclusion that extracellular palmitate had a similar cytotoxic effect on the IOMM Lee, CH157-MN, and AC599 cell lines that is being toxic at high doses and long-term exposure palmitate to all cell lines. Such palmitate exposure decreases cellular viability down to 10 or 5 (Figure 2). Furthermore, according to our dose response studies

Figure 1: Kill curve of IOMM Lee cell-line as a response to a variety of concentrations of palmitate from 100 μM to 700 μM

Figure 2: Kill curve of CH157 cell-line to different concentrations of palmitate treatment from 100 μM to 700 μM

Figure 3: Kill curve of BenMen 599 to different concentrations of palmitate treatment from 100 μM to 700 μM

we determined IC50 values of IOMM Lee, CH157-MN and AC 599 as 188,1 μM , 193,55 μM and 178,1 μM respectively. (Figure 1-3). At the same time IC50 values showed us that the amount of extracellular lipids tolerated by each cell line are comparable.

In the light of that finding, we examined kill curves to find a suitable range for further treatment aiming to

Figure 4: Relative gene expression of FABP6, AOX1 and SLC9A3R1 after 24-hour palmitate treatment. FABP6: fatty acid binding protein 6, AOX1: aldehyde oxidase 1, SLC9A3R1: sodium/hydrogen exchange regulatory factor

observe differential expression in genes patterns as a response to lipid exposure. So, we utilized 200 μ M BSA-palmitate treatment to model a lipid rich diet for all cell lines, keeping palmitate concentration as constant variable among all cell lines tested to analyze their varying response based on their grade. We decided on 24 hours which is a sufficient time to rewire gene expression in response to high, 200 μ M BSA palmitate in cells' environment.

3.2 Changes in the relative gene expression after palmitate treatment

Our ultimate objective is to discover the genes that are responsive to microenvironmental palmitate changes there by allow meningioma cells to adjust metabolically to lipid. From these genes, AOX1 was significantly changed as a response to palmitate treatment. AOX1, aldehyde oxidase 1, is a monooxygenase and have important roles for peroxisomal β -oxidation with redox reactions (6). It was upregulated in benign cell line, BenMen (AC599). On the other hand, AOX1 expression is downregulated for malignant cell lines: IOMM Lee and CH157 (Grade II) with a further diminishment of expression for IOMM Lee (Grade III). (Figure 4) The pattern in our data between benign (Ben Men 599) and malignant cell lines (CH157-MN and IOMM Lee) is in line with our expectations that we got from literature review (25,30). Our data suggests that down regulation of AOX1 might be a response malignant meningioma cells employ in order to adjust to changing lipid content in their media. Other target genes showed expected behavior in some cell lines while they did show unexpected results in other cell lines. Thus, there were no pattern between malignant and benign cell lines for other genes.

Figure 5: Relative gene expression of LRP2, CACNA1A after 24hour palmitate treatment. LRP2: LDL receptor, CACNA1A: alpha subunit of voltage gated Calcium channel

3.3 Discussion

Research over past decades confirmed the relationship between dietary habits and cancer: correlative studies between cancer progression and obesity have revealed that malnutrition can be a driver for worse prognosis for many cancers. In line with these findings, now we know a fat rich diet does not only increase the risk factor for cancer development, but also affects disease course and metastasis (1,2).

Recent studies show that many cancer types make use of external fatty acids as an energy source so that they can survive in the challenging conditions such as hypoxia or starvation. In addition to being used as an energy source, ingested dietary lipids may serve as biological building blocks and even provide precursors required for oncogenic signaling modifications, accelerating tumorigenesis. For example, adipocytes in lipogenic tissue cancers such as breast cancers can gear cancer onset, progression and metastasis. Hence, lipids in tumor microenvironment impact cancer progression especially in fat-rich tissues (3,11).

Similarly, tumors of the brain which is an extremely lipid rich tissue with %60 fat ratio, show aberrant fatty acid metabolism. Consequently, fatty acid (FA) metabolism emerges as a new focus in brain tumor research. Recently other groups discovered that glioblastoma multiform (GBM) pathogenesis relies on FA metabolism in order to rewire several essential biological processes on including anabolism, catabolism, regulation of ferroptosis, and generation of signaling molecules

(23). Hence a better understanding of FA biology can pave the way for development of better treatment options for GBM (24).

Similar to GBM, meningiomas, the most common adult intracranial tumors, show dysregulated FA metabolism. Moreover, irregular FA rewiring correlates with meningioma WHO (World Health Organization) grades (17, 25). Thereby, we sought to understand the role of dietary fatty acids in meningioma pathology. So, in our project, we investigated whether critical metabolic pathways are regulated in response to elevated external palmitate levels. Since it is known that tumors of different grades and genetic make-up respond differently to changes in tumor microenvironment (TME), in this study, we used meningioma cell lines from each grade and various genetic backgrounds(3,5). Those were namely: IOMM Lee representing Grade III (anaplastic) meningiomas, CH157MN (atypical) Grade II and AC599 Grade I benign meningiomas (28). In search for metabolic genes that are regulated by external palmitate levels and possibly utilized adapt to elevated palmitate levels in meningiomas we evaluated the RNAseq library we built for our cell lines: We used IPA as a tool to shortlist candidates for such genes. AOX1, SLC9A3R1, FABP6, CACNA1, and LRP2 were recognized as genes of interest by IPA. After a 24-hour, 200 μ M palmitate treatment, we used QPCR to assess the expression of potential genes. After analyzing the QPCR findings for differential gene expression, we found out that the expression of the AOX1 gene changes in response to increased lipid content in the cell medium.

AOX1 is known for its role in xenobiotic metabolism which essentially chemically converts substances into more easily excreted hydrophilic metabolites. AOX1 gene encodes an enzyme that catalyzes dehydrogenation of aldehydic compounds and esters to acyl-CoA. AOX1 participates in peroxisomal β -oxidation and its role this pathway is critical since AOX1 catalyzes the first and the rate-limiting step(6). At the same time, AOX1 facilitates oxidation of nicotinamide-adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP) to NADPH. Consequently, loss of AOX1 has been implicated in metabolic deregulation of prostate cancer, bladder cancer. Vantaku et al. demonstrated that the decrease of AOX1 expression elevated NADP, which in turn boosted carbon flux through the pentose phosphate pathway (PPP), nucleotide synthesis, and cell invasion. AOX1

down regulation was associated with malign behavior and tumor-promoting epigenetic reprogramming in these cells (19,22). We can speculate a similar adaptation to take place in malignant meningioma cells. More openly, we observed a downfall of AOX1 expression only in high grade meningiomas while benign meningioma even slightly increases AOX1 expression in response to same treatment. Since only malignant meningioma cell lines (CH157-MN & IOMM Lee) reduce AOX1 levels in response to elevated BSA-palmitate in the media and the amount of the reduction correlates with the grade of the cell lines, we hypothesize that fall in AOX1 expression is a metabolic adaptation those cells employ in order to keep up with the energy demanding malignant tumor growth. We suggest that decrease in AOX1, increases metabolic flux of fatty acids to alternative pathways like PPP and nucleotide synthesis. Thus, AOX1 mediated reprogramming of the metabolism ensures that fast dividing tumor cells have enough precursors for nucleotide synthesis and other important tumorigenic needs.

In addition to its role in xenobiotic metabolism, AOX1 is known to play a role in detoxification of drugs and can convert prodrugs to their active forms (6). Stavrinou and colleagues investigated these drug metabolizing enzymes in brain tumors and showed that there is a negative correlation between the WHO grade of malignancy and AOX1 expression on both transcriptional and translational levels in meningiomas (30). In parallel to these findings, we also observed differential expression of AOX1 in different grades of meningiomas upon dietary lipid exposure which indicates that AOX1 is also involved in regulation of FA metabolism of these tumors. Overall, our data strongly support the involvement of AOX1 in lipid metabolism of meningioma pathogenesis. In summary, manipulating AOX1 gene regulation and thus reprogramming meningioma metabolism could be a viable target to explore for effective meningioma therapy.

4. Conclusion

In our project, we illustrate the effect of changes of extracellular lipids on meningioma gene expression and viability in vitro. While our results show that extracellular levels of palmitate's influence on viability for all meningioma grades is comparable, cell lines differ in terms of their responsive expression profiles. Specifically, AOX1 gene significantly decreases with increased lipid content in malignant meningioma cell lines.

AOX1 downregulation in malignant cell lines compared to its upregulation in benign cell line, AC599 recapitulates previous literature *in vitro*. This data from our *in vitro* model adds new aspects to fatty acid metabolic studies on brain tumor, especially for meningiomas and summarizes effectively influence of lipids in tumor microenvironment on meningioma.

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This work is dedicated to memory of our beloved friend Menderes Karakaş

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8. Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table 1: Primer Sequences.

Target Gene	Forward Primer	Reverse Primer
<i>ACT-B</i>	<i>CAGCCATGTACGTTGCTATQÇAGG</i>	<i>AGGTCCAGACGAGGATGGCATG</i>
<i>FABP6</i>	<i>ATGGGCAGGACTTCACTTGG</i>	<i>CTTGTTGGTCATGGTGTGGC</i>
<i>AOX1</i>	<i>AAACAGAGTGCCTCTTCCCAG</i>	<i>TCCAGCACAGAGATAGGACAGA</i>
<i>LRP2</i>	<i>GTGCAGACCTAAAGGAGCGT</i>	<i>CTCGCCGTTCTTCCCC</i>
<i>SLC9A3R1</i>	<i>CCAGTTCATCCGGTCAGTGG</i>	<i>ACCTCCACAATGCGATCCTG</i>
<i>CACNA1A</i>	<i>GGAAAGAGAAGAAGGAGGAGG</i>	<i>TGGACAGGATGAACATGGAG</i>

7. Author Information

İrem YÜCEL: She is doing her PhD studies in the Coşkun Lab. She graduated from Molecular Biology and Genetics Department of Bilkent University. She is the co-supervisor in the Project. She guided students while they plan and perform their experiments and analysis. She contributed to the manuscript.

Buse Nur DENİZ: She was an undergraduate researcher and intern in the Coşkun Lab. She graduated from Molecular Biology and Genetic Department in Middle East Technical University in summer 2021. She performed overall experiments and analysis in our data and also helped to the manuscript.

Selin AŞCI: She was undergraduate researcher and intern in the Coşkun Lab. She graduated from Molecular Biology and Genetic department in summer 2021. She helped to the initial experiments in the Project.

Menderes KARAKAŞ: He was undergraduate researcher and intern in the Coşkun Lab. He conceptualized and planned of initial experiments in the Project.

Dr. Süleyman COŞKUN: He is the principal investigator at Department of Biology, METU. He is the supervisor of the projects who conceptualize the study and mentored our research group.

